

Indispensability of Nanotechnology in Agricultural Ecosystem

Ikenna Kelechi Ukabuiro

Department of Computer Science Abia State University, Uturu, Nigeria

Henry Odikwa Ndubuisi

Department of Computer Science Abia State University, Uturu, Nigeria

Abstract

This research is driven by the belief that nanotechnology has the potential to significantly improve agricultural practices, increase crop yields, reduce the use of harmful chemicals, and promote sustainable farming methods. This study delved into the revolutionary area of agricultural nanotechnology, evaluating its present use and prospective influence. This study analyzed the potential uses of nanotechnology using existing data by previous researchers, focusing on crop productivity enhancement while limiting resource consumption. The results obtained shed light on the various types of technologies used majorly in agricultural sectors and the study's goal is to discover best practices for the appropriate and long-term incorporation of nanotechnology in agriculture. The study provides insights on awareness, challenges, and future potential of nanotechnology in agriculture.

Keywords: *Nanotechnology, Nanoscale, Remediation, Photocatalysis, Graphene.*

Suggested citation: Ukabuiro, I.K. & Ndubuisi, H.O. (2024). Indispensability of Nanotechnology in Agricultural Ecosystem. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 1(2), 83-88. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2024.1(2).07

Introduction

Nanotechnology is the field of science and technology that involves manipulating and controlling matter at the tiniest scale, like atoms and molecules. It is the process of developing, modifying and controlling nanoscale components in order to generate new, creative materials and technologies for a variety of applications ranging from electronics and medical to energy and environmental solutions. It is a ground-breaking area of science and technology that has brought about significant changes in numerous sectors and different parts of the world.

Tanya & Lyna (2022) define nanotechnology as the study, design and application of microscopically small things. It is an exciting field that involves working with materials at the nanoscale, which is incredibly tiny, and it has opened up a world of possibilities for developing new materials, improving medical treatments, enhancing energy efficiency and countless other uses in many areas of life.

Among the much scientific advancement, nanotechnology has been identified as a potential technology for reviving the agriculture and food industry and can improve the livelihood of the poor. In this sector, nanotechnology plays an important role in crop production, food processing and packaging, food security and water purification, environmental remediation, crop improvement, and plant protection (Panuri et al., 2019).

The agricultural sector faces considerable problems, such as increasing food production to fulfill the demands of a growing global population while limiting environmental impact and resource waste. This research will look into how nanotechnology can help to address these issues by evaluating its role in maximizing resource utilization, enhancing crop management, and reducing agricultural impact on the environment.

The indispensability of nanotechnology cannot be overemphasized as it is essential due to the fact it allows for accurate nutrition and pesticide delivery, improves crop genetics for increased production and resistance, and provides solutions for sustainable farming. It reduces waste, optimizes resource use, and aids in the resolution of crucial issues in food production and environmental conservation.

The aim of this study is to examine the indispensable role of nanotechnology in agriculture while the objectives of the study include:

1. Evaluating and accessing the prospective uses of nanotechnology in agriculture, and as well as the current state of adoption.
2. To identify best practices for responsible and sustainable integration of nanotechnology in agriculture.

Materials and Methods

The research on nanotechnology is a wide and interesting scope that has evolved over the years and several methods has been developed including:

Application of Nanotechnology in Agriculture

This work recognizes agriculture as the backbone of developing countries, providing food for more than 60% of the population and how in order to achieve sustainable growth it must address issues such as crop production stagnation, low fertilizer efficiency, decreased soil organic matter and climate change, This research emphasizes the promise of nanotechnology applications in tackling agricultural difficulties, such as nano fertilizers, nano food, and smart treatment delivery systems (Ambily et al., 2019).

Nanotechnology-Based Water Quality Management for Wastewater Treatment

This study focuses on addressing the critical global issue of water contamination by pollutants, which poses a severe health challenge and the need for cost-effective wastewater treatment technologies. It explores nanotechnology's promising importance, highlighting nanoscale characteristics such as improved adsorption, enhanced photocatalysis, and high reactivity. The review focuses on cutting-edge treatment methods that involve nano-based materials like graphene, metal nanoparticles, and metal oxide nanoparticles (Madhura et al., 2019).

Evolution and Recent Scenario of Nanotechnology in Agriculture and Food Industries

This study acknowledges nanotechnology as an emerging force in food and agriculture, capable of modifying individual molecules and atoms. It reviews how the technology offers the potential to address various challenges in agriculture and food industries by manipulating substances at the nanoscale. (Vijayakumar et al., 2022)

Nanotechnology for Sustainable Agriculture

An Emerging Perspective by Sushila et al., (2021) emphasizes the role of nanotechnology in overcoming contemporary agricultural challenges climate change, stagnant crop yield, and pesticide resistance. For example, nanofiltration using materials like graphene, cellulose, and cyclodextrin improves water quality by removing salt, heavy metals, and organic pollutants, making it suitable for irrigation.

Enzymatic Bioremediation: a Smart Tool to Fight Environmental Pollutants

This study evaluates the prospective uses of nanotechnology in agriculture, assesses its impact on crop productivity, identifies best practices for integration, and promotes responsible and sustainable adoption. The research highlights the significance of nanotechnology in addressing challenges like climate change, nutrient deficiencies, and the need for more efficient agricultural methods. The study seeks to provide valuable insights into the current state of nanotechnology adoption in agriculture and its potential benefits (Lakhan and Navneeta, 2019).

Remediation of Soil Contaminated with Organic Compounds by Nanoscale Zero-Valent Iron

A review by Yaru Li et al. (2021) delves into the process of using nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI) for soil remediation due to its strong reducing ability. The study reviews different nZVI synthesis approaches, emphasizing aqueous-phase reduction with surface modification. The research discusses how these modifications enhance nZVI's efficiency in removing organic pollutants.

Efficacy of Nanoparticles as Nanofertilizer Production

A Review This study addresses the surging global demand for food that has led to substantial increase in fertilizer use globally. Traditional chemical fertilizers pose environmental challenges, as they are costly. To address this, the study explores biofertilizers as a safer alternative but acknowledges their limitations. Introducing nanotechnology-mediated nanofertilizers, the research highlights their potential to enhance plant productivity while minimizing environmental impact (Fatima et al., 2021).

A review on Positive and Negative Impacts of Nanotechnology in Agriculture

This research highlights nanotechnology's potential in various fields for sustainable development, focusing on applications in medicine, cosmetics, agriculture, and food technologies. Nanotechnology brings benefits like increased agricultural yield, improved cosmetics, and advanced medical sensors. However, concerns arise from the widespread use of nanoparticles, prompting the need for long-term analysis to assess environmental and biological impacts (Kumar et al., 2019).

In Overall, various assessments offers promising solutions to many challenges in agriculture, including improving crop productivity, reducing environmental impact, and ensuring food safety. However, further research and development are still needed to fully understand the potential risks and benefits of nanotechnology in agriculture.

The methods of Nanotechnology in agriculture involve the use of nanoscale materials and devices to enhance various aspects of farming and crop production. One application is the development of nanofertilizers, which are designed to deliver nutrients directly to plants in a controlled and efficient manner. These nanofertilizers can improve nutrient uptake, reduce fertilizer waste, and enhance crop yields. Another area where nanotechnology is being utilized is in the development of nanosensors for monitoring soil conditions and crop health. These sensors can provide real-time data on factors such as moisture levels, nutrient content, and disease presence, allowing farmers to make informed decisions and optimize their farming practices.

Additionally, nanotechnology also has the potential to revolutionize pest control in agriculture. Nanoparticles can be used to develop targeted and environmentally friendly pesticides that are more effective in controlling pests while minimizing harm to beneficial organisms and the environment.

Results

In other to achieve our stated research objective, sample analysis were conducted to provide solution and a proper representation of the different sectors in agriculture and the various nanotechnologies used in these sectors determined as shown in Figs 1, 2 & 3 below

Figure 1 shows different nanotechnologies and agricultural sectors.

Nanofertilizers	Crop Production	Improved nutrient absorption and enhance crop yield
Nanopesticides	Crop Production	Target pest control thereby reducing environmental impact
Nanoencapsulation in feed	Livestock Farming	Controlled release of nutrients for animals
Nanobiosensors	Livestock Farming	Monitoring animal health and detecting diseases
Nanoencapsulation in fish feed	Fisheries and Aquaculture	Enhance nutrient absorption and growth
Nanobiosensors	Fisheries and Aquaculture	Monitor water quality and fish health
Nanomaterials in wood materials	Forestry	Improve durability and resistance to pests
Nanosensors for forest monitoring	Forestry	Early detection of diseases and stress factors
Nanoencapsulation in food processing	Agribusiness and Agro-Industry	Improve packaging and preservation
Nanobiosensors	Agribusiness and Agro-Industry	Nanobiosensors: Enhance food safety monitoring
Nanomaterials for Soil Improvement	Agroforestry	Enhance nutrient retention and water holding capacity
Nanobiosensors	Agroforestry	Monitor plant health and soil conditions
Nanopesticides and Nanofertilizers	Horticulture	Targeted delivery for optimized plant growth
Nanosensors	Horticulture	Monitor plant health and optimize irrigation
Nanofertilizers	Agronomy	Improve nutrient management and crop efficiency
Nanosensors	Agronomy	Monitor field conditions and optimize resource use
Nanoencapsulation for seed treatment	Seed science	Enhance germination and early plant development
Nanomaterials for Stress Tolerance	Crop Physiology	Enhance crop resilience to environmental stressors
Nanobiosensors	Plant Pathology	Early detection of plant diseases.
Nanoencapsulation of Biopesticides	Plant Pathology	Targeted delivery for disease control
Nanomaterials for Crop Protection	Plant Protection	Improve resilience against pests and pathogens
Nanopesticides	Plant Protection	Targeted pest control

Figure 1. Nanotechnologies and Agricultural sectors

Figure 2 below shows a graphical representation of the sector analysis.

Figure 2. Pie Chart Representation of the Percentage of Various Sectors in Agriculture

Nanotechnology Application

Figure 3 below shows a representation of the application of nanotechnology in different agricultural sectors.

Figure 3. Bar Chart Percentage Representation of Nanotechnology Application

Discussion

The research was able to determine that Crop Production is the sector that uses the most nanotechnologies, with 11.5% and a total of 8 different nanotechnologies in use. This is likely due to the fact that crop production is the largest sector of agriculture while Nanobiosensors are the most common nanotechnology used in agriculture, with a total of 9 applications. This is likely due to the fact that Nanobiosensors are versatile and can be used to monitor a variety of environmental and biological parameters.

Conclusion

Nanotechnology is making strides in agriculture across various areas like crop production, livestock farming, fisheries, and more. Key applications include nanobiosensors, nanoencapsulation in feed and nanopesticides, serving purposes like monitoring animal and plant health and enhancing nutrient absorption. Predictions indicate a growing role for nanotechnology in agriculture, with potential benefits such as increased crop yields, reduced pesticide use, improved food safety and enhanced environmental sustainability. However, there are also concerns about nanomaterials entering the food chain and causing environmental harm, underscoring the need for further research to fully understand the pros and cons of integrating nanotechnology into agriculture.

References

- Ambily, E., Midhun, B., Annie, M. M., & Gold, M. S. (2019). *Application of nanotechnology*.
- Fatima, F., Hashim, A., & Anees, S. (2021). Efficacy of nanoparticles as nanofertilizer production: a review. *Environmental science and pollution research international*, 28(2), 1292–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-11218-9>
- Kumar, A., Gupta, K., Dixit, S., Mishra, K.K., & Srivastava, S. (2018). A review on positive and negative impacts of nanotechnology in agriculture. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16, 2175-2184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-018-2119-7>
- Lakhan, K., & Nayneeta, B. (2019). Enzymatic bioremediation. In K. Lakhan, B. Nayneeta, & P. Bhatt (Ed.), *: a smart tool to fight environmental pollutants* (pp. 99-118). India: Academic Press.
- Madhura, L., Singh, S., Kanchi, S., Sabela, M.I., Bisetty, K., & Inamuddin (2018). Nanotechnology-based water quality management for wastewater treatment. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 17, 65-121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-018-0778-8>
- Panuri, J. B., Sibyala, S., Bendangchuchang, L., & Allagadda, R. (2022). Nanobiotechnology mediated sustainable agriculture and post harvest management. *Curent Research in Biotechnology*, 4, 326-336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbiot.2022.07.004>
- Sushila, S. (2021, june 01). Ingentaconnect. Retrieved from <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/contentone/asp/jnn/2021/00000021>
- Hausman, T., & Griffin, L. (2022). *Nanotechnology definition, classification & Examples*. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/nanotechnology-definition-applications-examples.html>
- Vijayakumar, M., Surendhar, G., Natrayan, L., Pravin, P., Patil, P., Bupathi, R., et al. (2022). Evolution and Recent Scenario of Nanotechnology in Agriculture and Food Industries. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/1280411>
- Li, Y., Zhao, H. P., & Zhu, L. (2021). Remediation of soil contaminated with organic compounds by nanoscale zero-valent iron: A review. *The Science of the total environment*, 760, 143413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143413>